

Octahedral Complexes of Cobalt(II) *Bis* Ethylacetoacetate with Aromatic Heterocyclic Amines*

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Six-coordinated complexes of cobalt(II) *bis* ethylacetoacetate with heterocyclic amines like pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, ortho-phenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl have been isolated in pure crystalline forms having the formula $[\text{Co}(\text{Amine})_2\text{L}_2]$ or $[\text{Co}(\text{Amine})\text{L}_2]$ (where LH=a molecule of ethylacetoacetate). These are dull-red to orange yellow in colour. Conductance measurements indicate the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The electronic absorption spectra measurements exhibit only one ligand field band around 510 m μ corresponding to the transition $4T(F)_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{1g}$. The complexes are all paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff.}} = 4.8-5.1$ B.M.). Absorption spectra and magnetic moment identify the complexes as octahedral ones.

A *cis* configuration is assigned to the dipyridine, di- β -picoline or di- γ -picoline complexes on the basis of chemical evidence.

In a previous paper the preparation and characterisation of hexa-coordinated complexes of cobalt(II) *bis* acetoacetarylamides with aromatic amines were reported¹. The present communication arising out of immediate extension to similar systems, describes the adduct formation of cobalt(II) *bis* ethylacetoacetate with aromatic heterocyclic bases like pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, ortho-phenanthroline and α - α' -di-pyridyl.

Addition of dilute ammonia to an aqueous solution containing cobalt(II) chloride, ethylacetoacetate and pyridine results in the formation of dull red dipyridine *bis* ethylacetoacetate cobalt(II) complex. This can be recrystallised from benzene containing a trace of pyridine. Evidently cobalt(II) *bis* ethylacetoacetate is formed *in situ* and ammonia addition favours the *pH* for the formation of six-coordinated adduct. Other heterocyclic bases like β -picoline and γ -picoline react in a comparable manner. α -picoline does not furnish well-defined crystalline materials, which might be ascribed to the possible steric hindrance by the α -methyl group. These complexes lose the heterocyclic base when heated and are less stable than the corresponding nickel(II) complexes². In this respect these resemble the corresponding acetylacetonate³ and acetacetarylamide¹ complexes.

Action of bidentate chelating ligands like ortho-phenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl on the above complexes at ordinary temperature leads to the isolation of cobalt(II) heterochelates of the formula $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})\text{L}_2]$ (where AA=ortho-phenanthroline, α - α' -dipyridyl and LH=a molecule of ethylacetoacetate) with the liberation of heterocyclic base. These are yellow to orange yellow in colour. The heterochelates do not decompose and oxidise even on heating at 120°.

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1. Syamal and Dutta, *Ind. J. Chem.*, (in press.)

2. Syamal, *This Journal* (in press).

3. (a) Fackler, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 266.

(b) Syamal, *This Journal* (under publication).

The electrolytic conductance measurements of these complexes were done in methanol (conc. 0.002M) and molar conductance values (12-15 mhos) indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The stereochemistry of cobalt(II) complexes as indicated by magnetochemical and spectrochemical data is of much current interest. Hexa-coordinated cobalt(II) complexes are assigned spin free octahedral structures if their magnetic moments are in the range 4.7-5.3 B.M. If the values are in the range 4.3-4.7 B.M., the complexes are designated as tetrahedral structures^{4,5}. The magnetic moment of high spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes are higher than the spin only value due to very large orbital contributions arising out of orbitally degenerate ground states. From the observed magnetic moment ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=4.8-5.1$ B.M.) the structure of these complexes is inferred to be spin free octahedral.

Octahedral cobalt(II) complexes generally exhibit three absorption bands^{6,7} around 460, 550 and 1150 $m\mu$ associated with the transitions $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{2g}(P)$ (ν_1) respectively, whereas a band around 650-700 $m\mu$ (transition from $4A_{2g}$ ground state to $4T_{1g}$ state) is the characteristics of tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁸. The electronic absorption spectra of these complexes were recorded in mixed alcohols in presence of the respective heterocyclic base in the region of 350-1000 $m\mu$. Only one band around 510 $m\mu$ which is attributed to ν_3 band has been observed. While the dipyridine, di- β -picoline and di- γ -picoline complexes show a sharp band, the heterochelates containing ortho-phenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl give a shoulder. The ν_2 band was found to be missing which may be due to the weak character of $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(P)$ transition. Distinction can also be made between tetrahedral cobalt(II) and octahedral cobalt(II) complexes on the basis of molar extinction co-efficients. Tetrahedral cobalt(II) compounds generally show molar extinction coefficient of the bands of the order 10^2 , while the octahedral cobalt(II) complexes give a much lower value^{8,9}. In case of tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes the fine structure is caused by spin-orbit coupling which splits the $4T_{1g}$ state itself and allows the transition to the neighbouring doublet states to gain some intensity^{4,10}. The intensity of the complexes reported in this paper are quite low in comparison to other tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹¹ (Cf. fig. 1).

The instantaneous expulsion of two unidentate ligands by ortho-phenanthroline or α - α' -dipyridyl at ordinary temperature indicates presumably a *cis* octahedral structure for dipyridine (β -picoline or γ -picoline) complexes. If these complexes would

4. Cotton and Wilkinson, 'Advanced Inorganic Chemistry' (Interscience Publishers Inc., New York), 1962, p. 725.
5. (a) Figgis and Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 388.
(b) Busch, "Cobalt" (Reinhold Publishing Corporation), 1960, p. 123.
6. Ballhausen, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory" (McGraw Hill Book Co., Inc., New York), 1962, p. 258.
7. Costamagna and Levitus, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 2685.
8. Cotton, Goodgame and Goodgame, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4690.
9. Levitus and Ygupsky, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1589.
10. Krischner, "Advances in the Chemistry of the Co-ordination Compounds" (The Macmillan & Co., London), 1961, p. 419.
11. Madan and Donohue, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1617.

belong to the trans variety expulsion of monodentate base should have taken place at a higher temperature in order to initiate trans-cis isomerisation.

Fig. 1. Electronic Absorption Spectra of A $[\text{Co}(\text{py})_2(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.01M; R. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.01M and C. $[\text{Co}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.01M.

TABLE I

Analysis, colour, electrolytic conductance, magnetic susceptibility and electronic absorption spectral data of cobalt(II) complexes.

Compd.	Colour	Analysis				Molar conductance	μ_{eff} B.M.	Wave number ν, cm^{-1}	Molar absorbance litre mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
		Found		Reqd.					
		%Co	%N	%Co	%N	$\text{AM}^{\text{mhos}} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{mole}^{-1}$	(Temp. = 306°K)		
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dull red shining crystals	10.9	5.4	11.1	5.2	15	4.83	20,000-19,600	22.5
2. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dull red	10.9	5.3	11.1	5.2	15	4.80	,,	22
3. $[\text{Co}(\gamma\text{-Pic})_2(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dull red	11.1	5.5	11.3	5.3	12	4.83	,,	21
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen}(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Yellow	11.3	5.6	11.5	5.4	15	5.10	19,600-sh 19,200	50
5. $\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{eacac})_2] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange yellow	12.4	5.9	12.2	5.7	14	5.01	19,600-sh 19,200	50

where Py=pyridine, $\beta\text{-Pic}$ =3-methylpyridine, $\gamma\text{-Pic}$ =4-methylpyridine, O-phen=ortho-phenanthroline, dipy = $\alpha\text{-}\alpha'$ -dipyridyl and eacac=ethylacetoacetate.

*by loss at 110°C.

sh=shoulder.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate was a B.D.H.'s product. Ethyl-acetoacetate was E. Merck's (Germany) L.R. variety and used directly. Pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline were Hopkin & William's (England) product. Ortho-phenanthroline and $\alpha\text{-}\alpha'$ -dipyridyl were B.D.H.'s (England) product. Methanol used was of E. Merck's G. R. variety.

Conductance measurements were performed in methanol at 30°. Electronic absorption spectra were recorded in mixed alcohols (methanol, ethanol, 1:1) and small amount of the respective heterocyclic base except ortho-phenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl.

General method of preparation of cobalt(II) complexes: Two methods were utilised for the preparation of the complexes.

(i) *For adducts of cobalt(II) bis ethylacetoacetate with pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline.*— $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.002M) was dissolved in minimum amount of water and added to a mixture of ethylacetoacetate (0.004M) and the requisite heterocyclic base (1 ml.). The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6 by addition of dilute ammonia dropwise with stirring. Cooling in ice for few minutes appeared favourable. The dull red precipitate was filtered off and recrystallised from benzene containing a small amount of the base. These were dried in air.

(ii) *For cobalt(II) heterochelates.*—Dipyridine bis ethylacetoacetate cobalt(II) (1 mole) and ortho-phenanthroline / α - α' -dipyridyl (1 mole) were dissolved separately in minimum amount of ethanol. These two solutions were then mixed and allowed to stand half an hour with occasional stirring. The yellow to orange yellow crystals separated were filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol. The complexes were dried in air.

General properties of cobalt(II) complexes: The complexes are in general insoluble in water but soluble in methanol, ethanol and benzene. Whereas the pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline adducts decompose on heating, the adducts formed by the chelating ligands, ortho-phenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl are quite stable.

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